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The complex nature of the urban plastic soup

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Abstract

Millions of metric tonnes of plastic enter aquatic ecosystems annually, with urban environments acting as a primary source. Within cities, waterways such as rivers, streams, and canals collect and transport land-based plastic waste outside the city boundaries. While cities are a clear source of aquatic plastic pollution, the understanding of processes governing the journey of plastic through cities and the drivers of transport and accumulation within cities is limited. Here, we map the spatial distribution and temporal variability of plastic accumulation and transport across Amsterdam by using a database of nearly 10,000 monitored plastic items with monthly monitoring sessions between November 2022 and October 2023. Plastic accumulation and transport are neither uniform in space nor constant in time. We further identify and explore the explanatory power of urban environmental features within 250 m of the monitoring locations that may drive spatial patterns in plastic accumulation and transport. We reduced 87 urban environmental features to 8 principal components representing overarching urban contexts such as hospitality and public transport. By correlating these principal components with our plastic observations, we identify that spatial patterns differ substantially between the accumulation of plastics and the transport of plastics. While some plastic types are ubiquitous, others are restricted to specific contexts characterized by distinct combinations of urban environmental features. Most plastic types show no significant correlations with principal components, highlighting the complex nature and ubiquity of plastic in all urban contexts. We highlight that item-specific data is necessary to disentangle the complexities of urban plastic pollution. By analyzing which items tend to co-exist, potential clustering of items, and their abundance in the context of specific urban environmental features, we are getting closer to detecting the true sources and drivers of urban plastic pollution.

Keywords

Plastic pollution, Amsterdam, River plastic, Water quality, Urban environment, Single-use plastics

Introduction

Plastic pollution in the natural environment has led to persistent negative impacts on ecosystems worldwide¹. Estimates suggest millions of metric tonnes of plastic enter aquatic ecosystems annually, with urban environments acting as a primary source of this leakage²⁻⁴. As densely populated hubs of consumption, cities can be conceptualized as complex systems that ingest vast quantities of resources and energy, and excrete waste into the environment. Within cities, waterways such as rivers, streams, and canals act as pathways to collect and transport land-based plastic waste outside the city boundaries^{5,6}. While the role of cities as a major source of aquatic plastic pollution is clear, the understanding of processes governing the journey of

41 plastic through these urban aquatic environments and the drivers of the transport and accumulation within
42 cities is limited⁷.

43 The distribution and fate of macroplastics is driven by the dynamic interplay between moving water
44 and retention processes^{8,9}, which are assumed to be influenced by natural factors, anthropogenic factors,
45 and item characteristics¹⁰. Once plastic enters the water, it can get transported with its floating presence
46 depending on the buoyancy of the item and vertical or turbulent mixing^{11–13}. Transport at any point in
47 the system is a composite signal of plastics drifting from upstream sources and of direct inputs from the
48 immediate environment. Previous studies have explored the use of spatial characteristics and land use¹⁴
49 to explain variability in macroplastic pollution in urban riverine environments. For example, urban litter
50 abundance in Beijing is influenced by road networks, street-cleaning intensity, and by points of interest
51 (POIs) such as restaurants, parks, schools, hotels, and commercial areas¹⁵. Plastic hotspots in Purmerend,
52 the Netherlands, are clustered around train stations, shopping malls, fast-food restaurants, and many other
53 points of interest¹⁶. These findings motivate the use of spatially explicit approaches to identify potential
54 urban environmental features that drive macroplastic pollution. Plastics can be temporarily retained within
55 urban waterways, delaying their downstream transport from upstream sources and across different urban
56 zones. This may occur by mechanical entrapment, where items get stuck at bridge pillars, between quays and
57 (house)boats, or within other hydrological infrastructure¹⁷. It can also result from kinetic stagnation, where
58 low flow velocities, weirs, or dead ends in canals allow items to settle and accumulate¹⁸. Location-specific
59 retention conditions determine whether the observed floating plastics reflect local inputs or the accumulation
60 of items from upstream transport.

61 This study investigates the complex interaction of processes driving plastic accumulation and transport
62 within the urban waterways of Amsterdam. The interconnectedness of these waterways and water bodies,
63 combined with regulated water management, creates a complex environment for plastic movement. We first
64 characterize the spatial and temporal variability of plastic ‘stocks’ (accumulation) and ‘flows’ (transport) in
65 an urban setting across 20 hydrologically and geographically diverse monitoring locations¹⁹. This mapping
66 establishes an initial spatial overview for plastic distribution and transport throughout the water system over
67 time. Previous studies found few correlations between the temporal variability of plastics and environmental
68 drivers^{7,20,21}. While our data show temporal variability, we focus on explaining the spatial variation in
69 annually aggregated pollution data. We aim to identify the specific urban environmental features driving
70 spatial dynamics by analyzing land use, infrastructure, and human activity within a 250-meter buffer zone
71 at each location. We identified 87 distinct spatial variables capturing overarching urban contexts (e.g.,
72 hospitality, public transport) and reduced them to eight principal components. By correlating these principal
73 components with plastic observations, we can assess if specific environmental characteristics explain the
74 variability in the observed plastic abundance. Lastly, we evaluate the in(dependence) of spatial signatures
75 on the item-level using hierarchical cluster analysis and the Jaccard distance metric. This determines whether
76 different plastic items have a common spatial footprint, helping to clarify whether urban monitoring can be
77 aggregated or if specific item-level signatures are required to track diverse pollution sources.

78 **Methods**

79 **Study area and monitoring**

80 We analyzed accumulation and transport of floating plastics using a monitoring dataset at twenty hydro-
81 logically and geographically diverse locations across the Amsterdam urban water system¹⁹, (Figure 1). For
82 accumulation locations, all floating items within the most polluted 100 m² surface area were counted and cat-
83 egorized using the River-OSPAR categorization²². The boundaries were dynamically defined using Google
84 Earth polygons to consistently capture the most polluted area, regardless of geometry. Plastic transport was
85 estimated via visual counting from bridges²³. Bridges were divided into 1-3 segments depending on length,
86 where each segment was monitored four times in 5-minute intervals. Data was collected bi-monthly from
87 November 2022 to October 2023, alternating between two sets of locations to produce a complete monthly
88 dataset for all 20 sites. We used the ArcGIS Survey123 app to digitally log item counts, timestamps,
89 locations, and photos. All data and detailed calculations are available in a standalone dataset¹⁹.

Figure 1: Delineation of the study area with transport (yellow) and accumulation (purple) monitoring locations. The yellow arrows indicate the dominant transport direction. The white arrows indicate the flow direction of the IJ river, culminating in the North Sea. The first letter of each monitoring location indicates its city district. Figure adapted from.²⁴

90 Buffer zones and site-specific features

91 To investigate the connection between the urban environment and the observed plastic pollution, we gathered
 92 spatial information on the land cover, land use, and infrastructure in the direct vicinity of the monitoring
 93 locations. We first extracted water bodies as polygons from OpenStreetMap (OSM) and applied a 25-meter
 94 buffer to all waterways to limit our analyses to features in the direct vicinity of water. Next, we created
 95 circular buffers with a 250-meter radius surrounding all 20 monitoring locations. This radius is not arbitrary,
 96 but chosen as an effective proxy for the immediate human activity zone, corresponding to an approximate
 97 3-minute walking time^{25,26}. The activity generating the majority of single-use plastic waste (e.g., eating a
 98 snack from a store, smoking a cigarette at a bus stop) occurs within this range²⁷. A smaller buffer might fail
 99 to capture a key source, while a larger buffer might dilute the influence of the most direct sources. We then
 100 clipped the 25-meter waterway buffers to the 250-meter location buffers, manually removing disconnected
 101 areas or waterways that did not reach the monitoring location within 250 meters. The final buffers used in
 102 subsequent analyses are available in the supplementary material as a GIS GeoPackage.

103 For characterizing the monitoring locations, we gathered seven datasets from two sources (OpenStreetMap
 104 & Municipality of Amsterdam Maps Data) containing spatial information on the types of buildings, waste
 105 containers, POIs, traffic features, transport features, recreation areas, and shopping areas. After omitting
 106 doubles and clipping the seven dataset layers to the buffer zones, 87 distinct location-specific features re-
 107 mained, describing each of the 20 monitoring locations. These features were measured as either a total
 108 count (e.g, number of waste bins) or a total area (e.g, m² of commercial buildings). The full dataset used in
 109 subsequent analyses is available in the supplementary material.

110 Dimensionality reduction using Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

111 The large number of descriptive, location-specific variables ($n = 87$) complicated correlation analysis due
 112 to a high risk of multicollinearity when analyzing each variable individually against plastic observations²⁸.
 113 We used Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to identify the overarching commonalities of the 20 diverse

114 monitoring locations. This technique transforms the large set of potentially correlated variables into a more
115 manageable set of composite Principal Components (PCs)²⁹. Each PC captures a certain amount of the
116 total variance in the original dataset. Before the PCA, all location-specific variables were standardized by
117 converting them to Z-scores, measuring how many standard deviations a specific data point is above or
118 below the mean. This ensures variables with a large range (i.e., surface areas) do not disproportionately
119 influence the analysis compared to variables with smaller ranges (i.e., number of waste bins). We used a
120 scree plot to visualize the contribution of each PC and select the minimal set of components necessary to
121 explain approximately 80% of the total variance. For each remaining PC, the strongest positive and negative
122 contributing variables with loadings $\geq |0.1|$ were extracted in an attempt to characterize and interpret
123 the PCs. Lastly, we performed a Spearman’s rank correlation between the PC scores and the observed
124 quantities of floating plastic to determine if location-specific features can explain the variability in observed
125 plastic pollution.

126 Hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA)

127 We performed a hierarchical cluster analysis using the Jaccard distance (Equation 1) on the item observations
128 for both accumulation and transport locations to evaluate the co-occurrence and similarity in spatial occur-
129 rence of plastic item types. Unlike correlation-based metrics, the Jaccard distance measures the overlap of
130 item presence, while ignoring sites where both item types are absent, making it robust for sparse environmen-
131 tal data³⁰. In Equation 1, $|A \cap B|$ is the number of locations where both item types were found, and $|A \cup B|$
132 is the number of unique locations where at least one of the item types was found. We used this approach
133 to determine if a high spatial variability between individual item types requires a disaggregated, item-level
134 approach. We defined item communities based on their linkage distance D_J , where items always appear
135 together ($D_J = 0$), are strongly associated and generally found together ($0 < D_J < 0.3$), are sometimes
136 linked but also appear independently ($0.3 \leq D_J \leq 0.7$), generally appear independently ($0.7 < D_J < 1$),
137 or never appear together ($D_J = 1$). We limited the cluster analysis to categories with at least 10 items to
138 prevent bias from small sample sizes. Consequently, 51 of the 96 River-OSPAR categories were used. Lastly,
139 we correlated linkage distance with item mass and size (length + width) using the dataset by³¹ to explore
140 whether items of similar mass or size tend to have similar transport and accumulation patterns. Although
141 derived from riverbank observations, we assume the item size and mass properties are broadly representative
142 of plastics in Amsterdam, despite potentially lower fragmentation near the source.

$$D_J = 1 - \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} \quad (1)$$

143 Interactions at the land-water interface

144 The interaction and exchange of plastics between waterways and the land is unclear in riverine environments⁹.
145 To investigate the link between terrestrial debris and aquatic plastic abundance in an urban setting, we
146 performed a Spearman’s rank correlation between street-level pollution scores and floating plastic items. For
147 both plastic accumulation and transport monitoring, the pollution level on the land in the direct vicinity
148 of the monitoring location was estimated qualitatively. This was done by scanning the surroundings in a
149 360-degree panorama within 25 meters of the monitoring location. The assessment ranges from A (clean) to
150 D (heavily polluted) with criteria for the amount and type (organic v.s. non-organic) of litter (Figure 2).

151 Results and discussion

152 Spatial and temporal pollution patterns

153 Plastic accumulation and transport are neither uniform in space nor constant in time in Amsterdam²⁴.
154 This would imply that plastic transport might be controlled by a combination of predictable phenomena
155 and stochastic events. The monthly averages of plastic abundance in Amsterdam highlight the spatial
156 heterogeneity across the monitoring locations, both in composition and item counts (Figure 3a, b). While
157 cigarette filters and food wrappers are frequently found, their relative abundance differs between locations.

Score: A	Score: B	Score: C	Score: D
Impression: clean	Impression: predominantly clean	Impression: not clean, reasonably polluted	Impression: polluted
Criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No litter; • Or: only organic waste (e.g. branches, leaves) 	Criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1-3 pieces of litter • Non-organic litter 	Criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple pieces of litter • Non-organic litter 	Criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many pieces of litter • Non-organic litter

Figure 2: Qualitative evaluation of pollution on land in the direct vicinity of the monitoring locations, ranging from A (clean) to D (polluted).

158 For example, location C2 is strongly dominated by the transport of cigarette filters, whereas N2 and NW2
 159 are dominated by the accumulation of food wrappers. Drinking cans compose nearly a quarter of the
 160 accumulation at locations N1 and Z1, but only compose a small percentage (1.6%) of the transport at all
 161 monitored locations. Cigarette filters show a localized spatial pattern, where they are abundant in both
 162 transport and accumulation in the city center, while remaining virtually absent in accumulation locations in
 163 other city districts. These findings suggest that plastic composition and abundance are driven by site-specific
 164 land use features or local stochastic events rather than having a uniform distribution across the city.

165 There is temporal variability both in the composition and surface concentration of plastics, which indicates
 166 that the plastic dynamics within the city are not in a steady state (Figure 3c, d). Similarly, plastic pollution
 167 shows a dynamic spatial pattern. For example, the location that contributes the most to the total pollution
 168 varies from month to month (Figure 3e, f). This instability in time occurs for both the transport and the
 169 accumulation of plastic. The accumulated stock of plastic is higher during the winter months and early
 170 spring. This is evident from the peaks in January 2023 (1183 items) and in March 2023 (1257 items) (Figure
 171 3c). A sharp decline in the total number of items occurs in May 2023, remaining low during the summer and
 172 early fall. A few locations showed high accumulation consistently, where N2 and NW2 frequently contributed
 173 the largest share of the total accumulated items (Figure 3e). Conversely, locations Z1, W1, and C3 were
 174 constantly minor contributors. For plastic transport, in general, the total transport generally fluctuates
 175 between 200 and 400 items h^{-1} , with one extreme peak in April 2023, where the transport reaches 879 items
 176 h^{-1} , 2-3 times higher in comparison with the rest of the months. Locations C2, C5, and C6 often constitute
 177 50-70% of the total observed monthly transport (Figure 3f). Contrarily, O1A and Z2 consistently showed
 178 minimal transport of plastic.

179 Site-specific urban environmental features as drivers of local plastic spatial vari- 180 ability

181 Interpreting principal components of site-specific features

182 Each of the principal components extracted from the 87 location-specific variables emphasizes a different
 183 urban environmental feature of the urban landscape (Table 1). The first principal component (PC1) is
 184 dominated by high loadings on hospitality-related variables, such as restaurants, bars, and hotels. These
 185 variables reflect urban zones with dense human presence and consumption-related activity³²⁻³⁴. PC2 is
 186 characterized by strong positive loadings for waste disposal amenities and transportation infrastructure,
 187 along with negative loadings related to recreation & parks. In contrast, PC3 isolates public transport and
 188 traffic features with strong positive loadings and is negatively associated with waste infrastructure and
 189 mixed-use environments. PC4 relates to recreation-related features and parks, with high positive loadings

Figure 3: Spatiotemporal variation of monitored plastic observations from November 2022 to October 2023 with monthly average plastic observations of a) accumulation [items/100 m²] and b) transport [items/h]. The pie charts show the composition, highlighting the top ten items. The capital letters A-D in colored circles show the monthly average (rounded) street-level pollution scores. c) Sum and the top ten most abundant items in accumulation locations. d) Total and the top ten items in transport locations. e) Relative contribution of accumulation locations to total items per round. f) Relative contribution of transport locations to total items per round.

190 on playgrounds, sport fields, fountains, and green amenities. It has negative loadings for bicycle amenities
 191 (stores, rental, parking) and mixed built-up area. This component delineates leisure-dominated environments
 192 that may encourage longer visitor stays, potentially fostering different littering dynamics compared with
 193 high-traffic or hospitality-dominated areas^{35,36}. After these dominant axes, PC5-PC8 capture more subtle
 194 contrasts, not dominated by any specific location feature types but representing differences between services,
 195 residential areas, and specialized built-up areas (e.g., industrial, residential, and office zones).

196 Correlating plastic observations with principal components

197 The Spearman correlations between these PCs and the top ten plastic categories reveal that the spatial
 198 patterns of plastic differ substantially between accumulation and transport locations (Figure 4). In addition,
 199 some plastic types are widely distributed across principal components (including soft fragments, food pack-
 200 aging, and cigarette filters), while others are strongly associated with specific urban contexts (drink cans
 201 and bottles). Only a few correlations between the PCs and plastic observations are statistically significant
 202 ($p < 0.05$) for both accumulation (12.5%) and transport (6.3%), indicating that most plastic types do not

Table 1: The 87 location-specific variables reduced to eight principal components (PC1-PC8). All features with positive and negative loadings ($\geq |0.1|$) were summed in nine overarching categories: hospitality, stores & shopping, public transport & traffic, waste disposal, recreation & parks, other built area, services, and miscellaneous.

Urban context	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6	PC7	PC8
Positive contributors								
Hospitality	1.722	0.000	0.000	0.103	0.000	0.000	0.172	0.000
Stores & shopping	1.187	0.344	0.507	0.518	0.292	0.755	0.552	0.959
Public transport & traffic	0.000	1.111	1.524	0.539	0.000	0.142	0.214	0.358
Waste disposal	0.172	1.171	0.000	0.000	0.224	0.380	0.000	0.275
Recreation & parks	0.194	0.000	0.000	1.461	0.000	0.390	0.000	0.132
Other built area	0.000	0.387	0.458	0.333	0.584	1.327	0.747	1.003
Services	0.198	0.336	0.000	0.172	0.292	0.333	0.315	0.442
Miscellaneous	0.392	0.359	0.322	0.174	0.374	0.267	0.727	0.134
Negative contributors								
Hospitality	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.223	0.000	-0.129	-0.126
Stores & shopping	0.000	-0.147	-0.113	-0.397	-0.449	0.000	-0.805	-0.459
Public transport & traffic	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.124	-0.205	0.000	-0.982	-0.129
Waste disposal	0.000	0.000	-0.987	0.000	-0.443	0.000	0.000	-0.099
Recreation & parks	0.000	-0.716	-0.133	0.000	-0.360	0.000	-0.231	-0.126
Other built area	0.000	-0.265	-0.314	-0.672	-0.436	-0.206	-0.179	-0.371
Services	0.000	0.000	-0.155	-0.147	-0.121	-0.102	-0.138	-0.103
Miscellaneous	0.000	0.000	-0.155	0.000	-0.157	-0.232	-0.138	-0.333
Variance explained (%)	25.8	11.5	10.0	7.7	7.0	6.6	5.8	5.2
Cumulative variance (%)	25.8	37.3	47.3	55.1	62.0	68.6	74.4	79.6

203 exhibit strong or consistent correlations with specific urban contexts.

204 **Explaining accumulation patterns and correlations with urban contexts**

205 For plastic accumulation, the three most abundant item types (food wrappers, foam fragments, and soft
206 fragments) lack any significant or strong correlations with the principal components, indicating their accu-
207 mulation is diffuse rather than prevailing in specific urban contexts, despite their high overall abundance.
208 Only 22.4% of the total items are represented by item types (cigarette filters, drink cans, bottles, caps,
209 and lids) that show at least one significant correlation with PCs. We detected weak and non-significant
210 negative correlations between the hospitality sector (PC1) and the types of plastic. Even though these high-
211 consumption areas are associated with high (street) litter generation and abundance^{16,37,38}, the negative
212 correlations suggest rapid removal or dispersal from the source area rather than persistent local accumula-
213 tion. Locations with transportation infrastructure & waste disposal amenities (PC2) show strong negative
214 correlations with drink cans ($\rho = -0.83$) and bottles ($\rho = -0.85$), a moderate positive correlation with cigarette
215 filters ($\rho = 0.55$), while most other plastic categories show weak to moderate correlations. This contrasts
216 with the strong positive correlation of these items with PC4 (recreation and parks), which is attributable
217 to the negative association of PC2 with recreational spaces. This suggests that recreational areas and parks
218 in Amsterdam are both sources and sinks of littered cans and bottles¹⁴, which is substantiated by the
219 isolation of water bodies in city parks (e.g., location Z1), which restricts transport. The concentration of
220 cigarette filter accumulation near public transport infrastructure can be explained by high littering, despite
221 the presence of waste bins^{37,39}. Locations associated with transport infrastructure without waste disposal
222 amenities (PC3) are moderately correlated with caps & lids ($\rho = 0.55$) and cigarette filters ($\rho = 0.41$).
223 These correlations may reflect spurious or indirect associations rather than direct behavioral patterns, as
224 other “on-the-go” consumption items such as food wrappers and bottles show (very) weak correlations with
225 PC3. The alternating positive and negative correlations of drink cans and bottles with PC5-PC8 may reflect
226 the different composition of mixed urban areas. For example, the ‘other built area’ varies between principal
227 components (e.g., sports, arts, and offices in PC6, versus schools and swimming pools in PC5 and PC7). The

Figure 4: Spearman correlation matrices between plastic types and the principal components for accumulation locations and transport locations. Values with bold borders indicate statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). Plastic items are sorted from most (top) to least (bottom) abundant. PC1 is hospitality, PC2 is transport infrastructure & waste disposal, PC3 is public transport & traffic, and PC4 is recreation & parks.

228 fluctuations are likely a response to these highly specific local land uses. Nevertheless, because PC5-PC8
 229 capture a smaller fraction of the total variance than the first four PCs, these alternating patterns represent
 230 only local drivers of plastic accumulation. In general, diffuse accumulation may not be context-specific in
 231 mixed urban areas. For example, the strong correlations observed for cigarette filters and caps & lids with
 232 PC8 show these light items are universally present in mixed urban contexts, which is supported by.³⁵

233 Explaining transport patterns and correlations with urban context

234 For plastic transport, the correlations between most item types and PCs are more positive and higher,
 235 suggesting that more item types are associated with plastic transport across most urban contexts than
 236 with accumulation. Only 24.8% of the total items are represented by item types (soft fragments, cigarette
 237 filters, small bags, caps and lids, and other items) that show at least one significant correlation with PCs. No
 238 significant correlations were found between the observed plastic types and the first three principal components
 239 (PC1, PC2, and PC3). However, PC1 and PC3 exhibit strong negative associations with drink cans, bags,
 240 bottles, and food packaging, whereas PC2 shows a moderately positive association with these items. Cigarette
 241 filters and soft fragments show very strong, significant correlations with PC4 (Recreation & parks), despite
 242 the high shares of these items that are transported in dense city center locations (C2, C5, C6, Figure 3). This
 243 suggests the plastic entering the water might not be proportional to the local littering activity. Items may
 244 also be transported downstream or sink too rapidly to be captured within the 250-meter viewing window.
 245 The sum of items correlates strongly with PC4 and PC8 ($r = 0.60$ and 0.68 , respectively). This suggests
 246 that the urban commonalities captured by these components are stronger predictors of plastic volume within
 247 the 250-meter viewing window than accumulation site characteristics (Figure 4a).

Item-specific analyses reveal general spatial independence

The hierarchical clustering and correlation analyses (Figure 5a-b) reveal a decoupling between the physical properties of an item (mass and size, Figure 5c-f) and its spatial clustering behavior. Several items joined at short linkage distances ($D_J < 0.3$) are generally found together across sampling locations and monitoring rounds, suggesting shared sources, similar transport pathways, or comparable environmental behavior such as buoyancy^{8,11} and similar thresholds for (im)mobilization^{40,41}. For example, foam fragments and soft fragments ($D_J = 0.297$) co-exist in accumulation zones, possibly because of their shared fragmentation state, making them equally susceptible to kinetic stagnation in low-flow areas. Similarly, food wrappers and bags ($D_J = 0.250$), and drink cans and bottles ($D_J = 0.328$) form accumulation clusters that could point to shared sources as on-the-go consumption items. However, these clusters are the exception, as the majority of items are sometimes linked ($0.3 \leq D_J \leq 0.7$), or (generally) appear independently ($0.7 < D_J \leq 1$), suggesting the urban water system dynamics do not consistently sort items by type, size, or mass. This spatial independence is corroborated by a lack of correlation between linkage distance and item mass ($r = 0.04$, and $r = -0.05$) and the weak correlation between linkage distance and item size ($r = -0.29$, and $r = -0.03$). These correlations suggest that the hydrological sorting^{42,43}, typically driven by buoyancy, settling velocities¹¹, and wind speed, is effectively overruled in the Amsterdam urban context. Instead, the spatial transport and accumulation dynamics are influenced by mechanical entrapment and other stochastic processes regardless of item properties and hydrology. Additional inputs, such as localized littering or wind-blown litter from the streets, may further mask any underlying hydrological signal. This is particularly evident in transported items, where virtually all items have high linkage distances ($D_J > 0.4$) and the clusters with ($0 < D_J \leq 0.7$) generally consist of two or three item types only, except one cluster that includes six items. This heterogeneity in cluster size and lack of clear item communities reflects the dynamic nature of plastic transport in the urban water system.

The difference in clustering between accumulation and transport of plastic highlights the benefit of item-level resolution during monitoring efforts to understand plastic transport through urban waterways. Figure 5a and Figure 5b show that the numbers of clusters, linkage distances, and the item types within clusters differ substantially for transport and accumulation. For example, where food wrappers and bags tend to cluster together in accumulation zones ($D_J = 0.297$), they generally appear independently when transported ($D_J = 0.760$). Likewise, soft fragments and cigarette filters are more often transported together than separately ($D_J = 0.438$), but rarely accumulate together ($D_J = 0.903$).

Correlations at the land-water interface

The relationship between terrestrial debris and floating plastic abundance varies for accumulation and transport (Figure 6). For plastic accumulation, the correlation with qualitative street-level pollution scores is weak and statistically insignificant ($r = 0.09$, $p = 0.263$), suggesting that plastic accumulation is not predicted by or linked to the cleanliness of the immediate terrestrial vicinity. In contrast, plastic transport shows a significant though weak, positive correlation with the qualitative scores ($r = 0.27$, $p = 0.007$). The median transport rates gradually increase from category A to C, but decrease in category D (Figure 6b). This suggests that increased terrestrial litter abundance may be linked with increased plastic transport, but that heavily polluted streets may act as accumulation zones where litter is retained on land rather than being exported to the waterway. The lack of strong correlations shows that the interactions between the land and water are complex in an urban setting. Processes influencing plastic mobilization from land to water may operate at different spatial scales than those affecting waste abundance in the immediate surroundings because of transport and remobilization processes^{14,44}. For example, highly polluted terrestrial sites (Category D) may act as sources for downstream plastic accumulation, as the regulated system-wide flushing of the canals and water flow decouples local entry points from local accumulation zones.

Urban plastic dynamics and decoupling of accumulation and transport

Urban plastic pollution in Amsterdam is not a single, interconnected system but a mosaic of distinct and localized micro-environments, where the type of floating plastic in the environment is not strongly dictated by immediate surroundings and specific human activities, nor by city-wide spatial or temporal patterns. Our study supports that urban plastic dynamics in Amsterdam are not a well-mixed steady-state system

Figure 5: Hierarchical clustering with Jaccard linkage distance for all items in a) accumulation locations and b) transport locations. Items are strongly associated and generally found together where $0 < D_J < 0.3$, sometimes linked but also appear independently ($0.3 \leq D_J \leq 0.7$), and generally appear independently when $0.7 < D_J < 1$. Scatter plots with Spearman correlations between the linkage distance and c) mean item size difference (accumulation), d) mean mass difference (accumulation), e) mean item size difference (transport), and f) mean mass difference (transport). Mass and size data were used from.³¹

298 but rather a highly variable system characterized by a physical decoupling of stocks and flows. This suggests
 299 that the processes determining local plastic accumulation are likely decoupled from those driving system-
 300 scale transport, where physical factors or human activities might even operate at different spatial scales
 301 beyond the resolution of this study. Rather than acting as linear pathways, intertwined urban waterway
 302 networks function as systems of intermittent storage, similar to riverine environments^{5,45}. Dead-end canals
 303 and structures such as weirs, locks, and bridge pillars create stagnant zones for waterborne plastics to
 304 (temporarily) accumulate¹⁴. We found no evidence of spatial sorting of floating plastics by buoyancy, item
 305 size, or mass, suggesting limited influence of hydrodynamic processes on these properties at the studied spatial
 306 scale. Small heavy fragments and large buoyant items are equally likely to be trapped and transported
 307 in the same locations, driven by stochastic events and mechanical entrapment and release. The lack of
 308 any significant correlation between high-consumption hospitality zones (PC1) and local accumulation and
 309 transport suggests a flushing effect. Plastics generated or littered in these areas are either rapidly transported
 310 or removed, breaking the link between land-use source and aquatic sink.

Figure 6: Violinplots of a) accumulation locations and b) transport locations for each qualitative street-level pollution score as defined in Figure 2.

311 Spatial scale and the limits of local observations

312 Our analyses highlight the limitations of using local observation windows within a larger system, where
 313 key drivers and pollution patterns may operate at other spatial scales. This suggests a potential mismatch
 314 between the scale of monitoring plastic pollution and the scale of the physical processes driving plastic
 315 transport. When plastic enters the water, the direct spatial connection with its terrestrial origin starts
 316 to dissolve, making it difficult to trace an item back to a specific terrestrial input location. While the
 317 PCA captured nearly 80% of the variance in urban environmental features, only a small percentage of
 318 plastic abundance is significantly correlated with the urban gradients (12.5% for accumulation and 6.3% for
 319 transport). This suggests the PCA operates at a resolution that may miss microscale interactions among
 320 local hydrodynamics, specific urban environmental features, and plastic pollution at the land-water interface.
 321 As observed in broader riverine contexts, the mixture of plastics in the water rarely matches the mixture
 322 of plastics trapped in infrastructure⁴⁶. Our 250-meter buffers effectively captured local land-use signatures,
 323 yet they remain observation windows into a larger dynamic system. Since these buffers cannot account
 324 for the full trajectory of waterborne plastics, it follows that the true drivers of pollution operate at scales
 325 that extend beyond the immediate human activity zone, either at the micro scale of individual land-water
 326 interactions or at the macro scale of the entire upstream system. Resolving these challenges requires high-
 327 resolution monitoring. For example, cameras and machine learning can provide insights into the scale of these
 328 processes and provide high-frequency temporal data⁴⁷. Studies with GPS trackers could further highlight
 329 the moments in which plastics are mobilized from land to water and the speed at which they are transported
 330 once waterborne^{48,49}. This helps reveal how plastics move from their source to downstream hotspots, moving
 331 small observation windows into a larger system.

332 Implications for management and future outlook

333 The absence of strong, city-wide drivers for accumulation and transport implies that 'one-size-fits-all' miti-
 334 gation strategies may fall behind in efficiency and effectiveness^{24,50}. Although urban litter might aggregate
 335 in hotspots or around urban points of interest^{16,51}, city-wide spatial models remain insufficient for predicting
 336 its transport pathways and ultimate fate (Figure 4). Therefore, management strategies should shift from
 337 generalized waste infrastructure (e.g., adding more waste bins across a city) to targeted interventions based
 338 on local pollution patterns and item composition^{52,53}. For example, high-transport locations benefit from
 339 active interception devices, where accumulation sinks might need regular scheduled manual cleanups. The
 340 high abundance and clustering of bottles and drinks in recreational areas (PC4) suggest that upstream in-
 341 terventions could mitigate environmental leakage before plastic ends up as pollution. Implementing localized
 342 collection points or 'social bins', designed for easy collection by those in need, could prevent these items from
 343 entering the waterways. Future research and interventions need to move beyond reactive cleanup rounds
 344 and toward interception at the source²⁴. Quantifying the transport mechanisms that mobilize litter from
 345 streets into urban waterways is useful for identifying specific entry points or hotspots⁵⁴. It is essential to

346 conduct monitoring on the item level to evaluate the effectiveness of targeted interventions, as each item
347 may have entirely different urban pathways. Lastly, future work should aim to integrate camera systems,
348 deep learning models, and GPS tracking to align plastic monitoring efforts with accumulation and transport
349 processes operating at spatial scales beyond the direct surroundings.

350 Conclusion

351 This study assesses the spatiotemporal distribution and variability of plastic accumulation and transport
352 across Amsterdam. We found that urban plastic pollution in an intertwined network of canals is not a single
353 system, but a mosaic of distinct and localized micro-environments. Plastic accumulation and transport are
354 neither uniform in space nor constant in time, suggesting their dynamics are driven by a combination of
355 predictable phenomena and stochastic events. We demonstrate a decoupling of stocks and flows within the
356 system. Only a small percentage of the plastic variability (12.5% for accumulation, 6.3% for transport) is
357 correlated significantly with urban environmental features in the immediate surroundings. This indicates a
358 high spatial independence where the abundance and type of floating plastic are not strictly driven by local
359 human activity or typical hydrology. Furthermore, items do not cluster based on their mass or size, and the
360 clustering dynamics differ entirely between accumulation and transport.

361 These findings suggest that the drivers of urban plastic transport and accumulation are fragmented
362 and stochastic, resulting from mechanical entrapment, local hydrodynamic processes, and random events.
363 Consequently, spatial approaches for predicting pollution patterns remain limited. Because we cannot reliably
364 predict the ultimate fate of specific plastics, identifying primary entry points at the land-water interface is
365 crucial. The urban plastic soup is not a well-mixed, steady-state system, which further implies that ‘one-
366 size-fits-all’ mitigation and waste management strategies will fall short in both efficiency and effectiveness.
367 Therefore, evaluating targeted interventions requires item-level monitoring, as each piece of plastic is likely
368 to follow its own distinct pathway through the urban environment.

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376 Supporting information

377 The following files are available free of charge.

- 378 • Folder ‘Matlab dataset files’: contains all data sheets (.csv and .xlsx files) for the MATLAB analyses
379 and figures in this study.
- 380 • Datasets and availability online.xlsx: contains the metadata for the site-specific features dataset as
381 presented in the methods section.
- 382 • matlab_script.m: contains all code used in the analyses and creation of the figures in this study.
- 383 • monitoring_location_buffers.gpkg: GIS geopackage of the 250-meter buffer areas of the twenty moni-
384 toring locations.

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